

Dear Editor Mirosław Staron,

We would like to sincerely thank you and the reviewers for the consideration and time devoted to our manuscript.

We are pleased to resubmit our work entitled “Understanding Undesirable Attributes of Requirements Engineer” (INFSOF-D-25-01421). We prepared this new version of the manuscript to address all recommendations and comments.

In summary, the main changes done in the manuscript were:

- Clarifying the research method.
- Adding further details regarding the categories and their corresponding undesirable attributes.
- Comparing desirable and undesirable attributes.
- Including complementary material encompassing the research method description, codebook, and threats to validity.

Attached below is a rebuttal letter detailing all changes and answers to the recommendations and comments. All changes made in the manuscript are highlighted in blue color. Also, as requested, all changes are annotated with line number in our response. It is important to note that addressing the reviewers’ comments required the inclusion of additional material. Consequently, the manuscript slightly exceeds the maximum length of 2,500 words.

Sincerely,

Larissa Barbosa Leôncio Pinheiro

Savio Freire

Marcos Kalinowski

Zadia Codabux

Rodrigo Spinola

Manoel Mendonca

Rita Suzana Pitangueira Maciel

Description of Changes

Reviewer #3 The authors have addressed most of my previous concerns, and the revisions have improved the overall quality of the article. However, one remaining concern has not been addressed.

We really thank Reviewer 3 for the careful revision of the manuscript as well as valorous comments and suggestions. We detail below the action made for each comment. All changes made in the manuscript are highlighted in blue color.

Comment #1:

In the Results section, the survey findings still lack quantitative analysis. There is no presentation of numerical percentages, statistical tests, or any other quantitative metric that would allow readers to assess the strength, distribution, or significance of the findings beyond a simple mention of "most cited."

Answer: We appreciate your comment. We think it is better to explain this issue. We include the percentages of each desirable attribute listed in Section 3. We also provide the complete list of undesirable attributes with their corresponding number of mentions and quotes available at Zenodo replication package.

Comment #2:

While I recognize that this is a short communication paper, the current Results section reads more like a qualitative thematic summary and does not satisfy the request for quantitative analysis expected even for a journal short paper.

Answer: We sincerely appreciate your comment regarding the qualitative nature of our work used to identify undesirable attributes of requirements engineers. Based on this analysis, we describe these attributes and provide their corresponding number of mentions in our Zenodo replication package.

As suggested, we included the percentage of mentions for the attributes discussed in Section 3. For the remaining attributes, interested readers can refer to the Zenodo replication package for detailed information.

Reviewer #4 I want to thank the authors for the interesting work and their submission! It is indeed important to explore the opinions of industry practitioners about the attributes of requirements engineers.

Despite the importance of the work, there are some issues that require at least a thorough revision, or possibly resubmission as a full paper rather than a short communication.

We really thank Reviewer 4 for the careful revision of the manuscript as well as valuable comments and suggestions. We detail below the action taken for each comment. All changes made in the manuscript are highlighted in blue.

Comment #1:

My main concern is that the work in its current form is not self-contained - it raises more questions than it answers. There is no discussion of the findings in the context of existing studies, nor is there a discussion of the findings in relation to the authors' prior study on desirable attributes.

We thoroughly revised our article to make it self-contained and discussed our findings in contrast to previous literature.

Comment #2:

My second main concern is the methodology, which is not clearly presented and therefore requires more detailed reporting. Specifically, it is not clear why the survey was conducted before the interviews, nor how the survey results were analyzed without definitions. In fact, in the interviews, no "supporting evidence" was collected; instead, survey results were complemented with definitions of the undesirable attributes identified in the survey. It is unclear why open coding was applied to only half of the transcripts, and details about the coding process are missing. Finally, there is no discussion of the implications of conducting interviews with only 11 out of 18 survey participants, nor of the time lag between the survey and interviews.

I suggest the authors conduct a major revision of the submission to make it self-contained and suitable for the short communication format. However, I think that it may be very difficult to fit this research into this format. I encourage the authors to consider submitting the study as a full paper, because the next revision may not allow inclusion of all the required details in a short communication (e.g., clear reasoning about attribute categorization, discussion of undesirable attributes in the context of previous work on desirable attributes, sufficient discussion of threats to validity, discussion of undesirable attributes in relation to existing literature, etc.). If such details are missing after the revision, it would be more appropriate to reject the submission.

Answer: To clarify our methodology and other related characteristics, we have made available a document with the complete methodology. It is available from the Zenodo replication package.

Comment #3:

P.1:

Abstract

"Although several studies have examined software professionals' characteristics, often overlook the human-centered nature of requirements engineering, where interpersonal and communication skills are critical."

I would not start the abstract (or any section) with "although".

"often overlook" - who/what often overlooks? The sentence seems to be incomplete.

"Human-centered" may be interpreted as a contested claim that requires further clarification (which is difficult to provide in the abstract). Isn't the purpose of RE to support software engineering in implementing software? If yes, then it may appear more system-centered.

"hat may hinder collaboration" -> "that may"

Context should connect well to objectives. From the context, it is not clear why this study focused on undesirable attributes and not desirable attributes, which are overlooked. It is important to fix this as it breaks the reading flow.

"We surveyed software practitioners to identify these attributes and conducted interviews to gather supporting evidence."

Gather supporting evidence of what? Of the undesirability of these attributes? It would be better to somehow articulate the relation between the methods that you have used (e.g., we used method B to validate/extend the results obtained from method A). This is important

because you also started with a survey. And then conducted interviews, which, in my opinion, is a bit unconventional.

"The maps help requirements engineers reflect on and improve their professional practice by recognizing traits that may hinder collaboration and project outcomes."

The conclusion that the maps help practitioners emerges very unexpectedly. How have you identified it? Have you conducted validation/evaluation during the interviews? It is not apparent from the methodology description.

Answer: We appreciate your review of our abstract. We rewrite it following your comments:

- The characteristics of software professionals have been widely investigated in the literature. However, limited attention has been given to undesirable attributes in Requirements Engineering, despite the strong dependence of this activity on stakeholder interaction and collaboration.

Comment #2:

Page 2:

Introduction

"Because this role depends heavily on interaction"

What kind of interaction? Interaction with whom? For example, interaction may include stakeholders, team members, or systems (human-computer interaction), which is also relevant to requirements engineers.

The submission makes some effort to explain why investigating undesirable attributes is necessary in addition to studying desirable ones. However, it does not fully clarify this point. Why are undesirable attributes not simply the negation of desirable ones? Are they fundamentally different? Given that the study references the authors' prior work on desirable attributes, a comparison is expected later.

Answer: Following your comment, we improve the Introduction section, as follows:

- Requirements engineers bridge human needs and technical solutions, translating stakeholder expectations into actionable requirements. The activity performed by the requirements engineer depends heavily on the interaction between stakeholders, team members, and undesirable behaviors or attitudes can compromise collaboration and, ultimately, project outcomes.

Comment #3:

Research Method

"We followed the approach adopted by Kalliamvakou et al. [3] and Dias et al. [4]."

Please explain which approach was exactly taken, not just put references. Is it an approach to conduct a survey first and then interviews?

Answer: We clarify the need of surveying the participants and after interview then, as follows:

- As we did not have a previous list of attributes, we first designed a survey to identify desirable and undesirable attributes of requirements engineers. Afterwards, we invited eighteen software practitioners from our Brazilian industrial partners, but only 11 of them were available for interviews and for answering the follow up question. This approach was adopted from Kalliamvakou et al. [3] and Dias et al. [4].

Comment #4:

What industry do participants work in? Undesirable attributes of requirements engineers can vary significantly across industries; it is important to report this.

Answer: All participants are from the Brazilian software industry. We highlight it in:

- However, we acknowledge that our sample comprises 18 participants from the Brazilian software industry may introduce contextual bias. Shared industry practices, as well as geographical and cultural factors, may influence participants' perceptions. To mitigate this threat, we included professionals with diverse experience levels, company sizes, and career trajectories. Furthermore, Brazil's economic and cultural diversity may partially reduce regional bias.

Comment #5:

If I understand it correctly, the initial analysis of attributes was based on the survey of 18 participants, and definitions were elicited later in the interviews with 11 of the surveyed practitioners. This raises many questions.

How was the initial analysis of the survey results conducted without definitions?

What are the implications of excluding seven surveyed practitioners from the interviews in which definitions were elicited?

What are the implications of eliciting definitions later, after conducting a survey on attributes? Participants could give a definition differently from how they would define an attribute during a survey.

Answer: Your understanding is correct. We conducted the initial analysis by examining the list of attributes provided by the participants to identify similarities, that is, two or more attributes with the same meaning. Although we elicited the definitions later, the participants recognized the attributes they listed in the survey, reducing the threat regarding a different definition of the attribute. Since we interviewed 11 professionals in the field, some undesirable attributes were not investigated further. We mean that these attributes lack a definition and we were unable to relate them to the others. We clarify these points in the supplementary material.

Comment #6:

It is reported that open coding was applied to half of the transcripts. Why only half? Was any other analysis executed on the other half?

Answer: In fact, two researchers, each of them, individually coded half of the transcriptions and revised each other. We rewrite the paragraph to explain your comments.

- After transcribing the interviews, the same researchers applied open coding [5] of the transcripts to capture the main ideas in each response. Each of them, individually, coded half of the transcripts and then revised each other. Afterwards, they met with the last author to resolve the divergences, resolving disagreements with a third researcher. In the end, we produced a consolidated set of codes representing the key concepts of each attribute.

Comment #7:

Detailed demographic information about the participants (experience, the number of companies they worked for, etc.) should be moved to the beginning of the section where you mention the number of participants.

Answer: Following your comment, we moved to the beginning:

- Participants had between one and thirty years of experience (average = 10 years) and had worked for an average of six companies (range: one to twelve). They represented organizations of different sizes: small (up to 50 employees; n = 2), medium (51–1,000 employees; n = 6), and large (more than 1,000 employees; n = 10). The sample included ten software engineers and eight project managers.

Comment #8:

Page 3:

Results

Reported results miss some additional explanation of the reasoning behind categorization and a more detailed description of attributes and categories. For example, "(i) difficulty in relationships means the challenges that affect team dynamics" - How about relationships with customers? They are outside of the team, but I still assume difficulty in relationships with them was probably also named by the practitioners.

Simultaneously, in the description of the personality-related attributes category, interaction with stakeholders and not team members is emphasized.

Answer: Thanks for your comment. We agree that relationships difficulties may also involve customers and other stakeholders outside the team. For example, one participant reported that some requirements engineers "think they will solve everything alone" and "cannot handle the complexity alone", reflecting difficulties in collaboration with others involved in the project, not only team members. We updated the "difficulty in relationships" definition in the new version of the paper.

Regarding personality-related attributes category, our data also included individual characteristics that affect how requirements engineers organize and conduct their work. We updated the category definition accordingly.

Lastly, to support a detailed view of the categories and their corresponding attributes, we included a code book in the complementary material.

Comment #9:

"c) Technical, revealing issues in performing RE activities"

The name of the category is very confusing. Does it mean "technical undesirable attributes of a requirements engineer"?

The other names of categories should also be clarified. For example, "domain knowledge" -> "domain knowledge (related) attributes."

Answer: Following your comment, we redefined the name of the categories:

- a) Communication, expressing issues on how requirements engineers communicate (e.g., difficulty in relationships), b) Lack of Domain Knowledge, grouping attributes (e.g., wait for the user to have all the answers) to reduce the business knowledge; c) Lack of Technical knowledge, revealing lack of technical skills that are used in RE activities (e.g., lack of knowledge of RE practices and artifacts); and d) Personality, with attributes

related to express how requirements engineers think, feel, and behave in their interaction with stakeholders (e.g., impressive).

Comment #10:

"d) Personality, with attributes related to expressing how requirements engineers think, feel, and behave in their interaction with stakeholders (e.g., impressive)."
This sounds to me as communication related attribute because interaction is emphasized.
What exactly does "impressive" mean in this context?

Answer: Following your comment, we reviewed the categories and their corresponding attributes. We realized that *impressive* is better grouped into the Personality category. We also renamed *impressive* to *being impulsive*, as it means acting impulsively without considering stakeholders' needs and consequences.

Comment #11:

In some cases, more examples would be beneficial. Example "wait for the user to have all the answers" sounds more like the passivity of a requirements engineer related to personality or communication, and not a domain knowledge attribute.

Answer: As we could not interview all participants, some attributes do not have explicit definitions. "Wait for the user to have all the answers" is one of them. We categorized it into domain knowledge because it suggests relying exclusively on users instead of actively seeking to understand the system domain.

Comment #12:

Also, the provided explanation of categories does not draw a clear difference between domain knowledge and business knowledge. Indeed business knowledge is one type of domain knowledge, but they are not synonymous.

Answer: We appreciate your observation regarding these concepts. The *Domain knowledge* category also encompasses *business knowledge*, as evidenced in the following quote: "Sometimes the analyst is very new to the area, to the company, and doesn't know the business, can't explain the business rules. There are very complex business areas, so they don't know them and can't explain them to the developer. The developer ends up needing to understand some of this, which should have been passed on by the requirements analyst, detailing the requirements, and clearly stating what needs to be done." We updated the concept of the *Domain knowledge* category.

Comment #13:

Page 4:

Figure 1:

Names of the attributes and concepts (definitions) could be refined for better conciseness. For example, the name of the attribute "MAKE SUPERFICIAL SPECIFICATIONS (WITHOUT DETAILS, WITH INCONSISTENCIES, AMBIGUITIES - MAKING THE TEAM'S WORK DIFFICULT" in category D (Technical) is definitely too long, and there is a missing parenthesis.

Answer: We appreciate the reviewer's comment. We think it is better to explain this issue. The attribute names were raised through the responses of our participants and therefore some are long. The parenthesis has been corrected in the figure.

Comment #14:

Adding references to participants does not make sense because there is no overview of demographic information about participants. Moreover, it is not clear if these are references to survey or interview participants.

Answer: References to participants are used to show how the qualitative analysis of attributes was conducted among the reviewers, and these references are deduced from the interviews, as can be seen in the complete methodology available on Zenodo.

Comment #15:

"It is worth noting that not all 17 attributes have their definitions, as some were not addressed during the interviews."

Indeed, because the authors have not interviewed all the survey participants, and this is not discussed appropriately anywhere, as one of the main limitations.

Answer: We discussed this as a threat to validity, along with others. It is available in our supplementary material on Zenodo.

Comment #16:

Page 5:

Conclusion

I would like to second the Reviewer #1 from the previous round of review – discussion in the context of existing literature is missing and is very much required. For example, the role of domain knowledge was empirically explored in the previous RE studies, and there is no decisive answer whether it is good or bad for a requirements engineer to have domain knowledge. The conclusion in some of the studies was that, in fact combination of team members having domain knowledge and those without domain knowledge is important for effective generation of new ideas or improvement of the effectiveness of the requirements engineering team (Niknafs, A., & Berry, D. M. (2012, September). The impact of domain knowledge on the effectiveness of requirements idea generation during requirements elicitation. In 2012 20th IEEE International Requirements Engineering Conference (RE) (pp. 181-190)).

Answer: Thanks for reference. You improve the comparison with the technical literature considering Niknafs and Berry's results:

One point particularly caught our attention. While Niknafs and Barry-\cite{8} suggested that combining team members with and without domain knowledge can improve idea generation and team effectiveness, our findings identified lack of business knowledge as an undesirable attribute for requirements engineers.

Comment #17:

Moreover, the authors do not make any connection to their study on the desirable attributes of a requirements engineer.

Answer: We compared the desirable and undesirable attributes and included the following statement in the paper:

We also compared the desirable attributes [2] with undesirable ones, showing that both are associated with communication, collaboration, organization, stakeholder interaction, and

adaptability, highlighting the importance of interpersonal and organizational competencies in requirements engineering. However, the findings also indicate that undesirable attributes are not simply the negation of desirable ones. While some contrasts exist, such as communication skills versus lack of communication, several undesirable attributes involve restrictive behaviors, such as resistance to change and poor interpersonal relationships, whereas desirable attributes are associated with proactive behaviors, including initiative, negotiation, and problem-solving. Overall, the results suggest that desirable and undesirable attributes represent different dimensions of professional behavior rather than direct opposites.